

TIME SERIES ANALYSIS AND STOCK PRICE PREDICTION USING FFT AND PYTHON

(Analisis Siri Masa Dan Ramalan Harga Saham Menggunakan FFT Dan Python)

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ABSTRACT

There are various methods for predicting stock price patterns mostly involving machine learning. This makes it difficult for people who do not have a background in machine learning to use the method. Forecasting stock price patterns is very important and useful for people who are new to the field of stock investment. In fact, stock price pattern predictions are also very useful to people who have already ventured into the field of stocks. This is because through the results of this forecast, they can plan when the time is right to buy or sell stocks in order to avoid huge losses. The main goal of this project is to use time series analysis and predict the stock price patterns using FFT graphs that will be generated using the Python software. Stock closing prices are used to build graphs in the time domain as well as FFT. The share prices used for this project are from domestic and foreign companies. For domestic companies, Bursa Malaysia Berhad and Maxis Berhad were selected for this project. As for overseas companies, Apple Inc and Tesla Inc have been selected. Data which are the closing price of shares for each company is recorded within a period of 5 years. Time domain graphs and FFT graphs are constructed using the data. An analysis conducted on the FFT graphs obtained was to identify the peak values. Through these peak values, we will be able to know the stock price cycle. Finally, through the cycle, we will be able to know when the highest price of the stock occurs and how many cycles for each year.

Keywords: Stock closing price; Pattern; Time domain; FFT; Python

ABSTRAK

Terdapat pelbagai kaedah untuk meramal corak harga saham tetapi kebanyakannya melibatkan pembelajaran mesin. Hal ini menyebabkan orang yang tidak mempunyai latar belakang dalam bidang pembelajaran mesin sukar untuk menggunakan kaedah tersebut. Ramalan corak harga saham sangat penting dan berguna bagi orang yang baru berjinak dalam bidang pelaburan saham. Malah, ramalan corak harga saham juga sangat berguna kepada orang yang telah menceburi bidang saham. Hal ini adalah kerana melalui keputusan ramalan ini, mereka dapat merancang bila masa yang sesuai dan tepat untuk membeli atau menjual saham supaya dapat mengelakkan kerugian yang besar. Matlamat utama projek ini adalah untuk membuat analisis siri masa dan meramal corak harga saham menggunakan graf FFT yang dijana menggunakan perisian Python. Harga tutup saham digunakan untuk membina graf dalam domain masa dan FFT. Harga saham yang digunakan bagi projek ini adalah terdiri daripada syarikat dari dalam negara dan luar negara. Bagi syarikat dalam negara, Bursa Malaysia Berhad dan Maxis Berhad dipilih untuk projek ini. Bagi syarikat luar negara pula, syarikat Apple Inc dan Tesla Inc telah dipilih. Data iaitu harga tutup saham bagi setiap syarikat direkodkan dalam tempoh masa 5 tahun. Graf domain masa dan graf FFT dibina menggunakan data tersebut. Analisis dijalankan ke atas graf FFT yang diperolehi untuk mengenalpasti nilai puncak. Melalui nilai puncak tersebut, kita akan dapat mengetahui kitaran harga saham. Akhirnya melalui kitaran tersebut kita akan dapat mengetahui bila harga tertinggi saham berlaku dan bilangan kitaran setiap tahun.

Kata Kunci: Harga tutup saham; Corak; Domain masa; FFT; Python

INTRODUCTION

Shares are proof of ownership of a company or enterprise in the form of limited individuals.

There are 3 types of stocks namely limited risk, full control and balance claims. The stock market is a key element in financial markets and it has always been important to economic policies and planners. This project is a stock price prediction project using

FFT with stock closing price. Graphs are built using Python software. Then, the graphs are analyzed to be able to make hypotheses based on the results obtained. This project aims to predict stock price patterns.

METHODOLOGY

In this project, the closing price will be used to build the time domain graph as well as the FFT graphs. The data are the closing price of the stock taken through Yahoo Finance website and saved using Microsoft Excel. Data were taken for a period of 5 years to get more accurate results.

This project focuses on the closing price of shares for domestic and foreign companies. For domestic companies, Bursa Malaysia Berhad and Maxis Berhad were selected for testing. For overseas companies, Apple Inc. and Tesla Inc. in turn has been selected. This project uses Python to create the graphs that is needed for the analysis.

One of the reasons Python shown in Figure 1 was chosen for this project is because it is a free source of programming language and user friendly. Python consists of a broad of standard libraries.

FIGURE 1. Python logo

TABLE 1. Example of data stored for 5 days duration

Date	Open	High	Low	Close	Adjusted Close	Volume
07/08/2020	10.60	10.64	10.28	10.36	10.36	3,755,100
06/08/2020	10.80	10.88	10.30	10.44	10.44	4,481,000
05/08/2020	10.18	10.90	10.18	10.60	10.60	13,780,800
04/08/2020	9.65	9.95	9.35	9.85	9.85	6,135,200
03/08/2020	9.30	9.80	9.13	9.60	9.60	6,596,100

Before constructing a time domain graph and an FFT graph, the sequence of data needs to be changed slightly by performing a zero-padding process. Due to the fact that the number of data sequences is only one thousand two hundred and sixty-one, we need to add zero values to the data until we reach a certain number of data sequences to fit the standard FFT algorithm.

For example, the data sequence in this project was changed to reach two thousand forty-eight data sequences. This process will facilitate the building x-axis in the graph. Next, for the construction of the FFT graph, the y-axis is converted to nitude and the x-axis is converted into a daily cycle through the FFT process through the FFT graph that has been obtained, there is a problem with the graph that is the value of DC component on the graph is very large. This makes the process of determining patterns at high frequencies difficult to perform. This problem is also known as "DC Bias" or "DC Offset".

Time domain graphs and FFT graphs are built using Python software. For the construction of the time domain graph, the closing price of the stock

will be set on the y-axis and the date will be set on the x-axis in the graph. Next, for the construction of the FFT graph, the y-axis is converted to magnitude and the x-axis is converted into a daily cycle through the FFT process A new sequence of data with a zero average is generated.

Calculations were performed using original data that is data that did not undergo a zero-padding process. Before building an FFT graph, the newly obtained data must go through zero-padding process in order to comply with the standard FFT algorithm.

A new sequence of data using the formula below is used:

$$x'(n) = x(n) - x_{ave}(n) \tag{1}$$

where $x'(n)$ is the new sequence, $x(n)$ the current sequence and $x_{ave}(n)$ the average value

Next, once the peak values have been found on the newly obtained FFT graph, the frequency of the peak values can be found using the formula below:

$$f_m = \frac{mf_s}{N} \tag{2}$$

where f_m is the frequency of the peak value, m is the peak value sample, f_s is the sampling frequency and N is the number of data. For the time domain graph, the peak value of each year can be identified. After that, some conclusions about the the stock price increase can be made.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are three types of graphs in this section, namely graphs in the time domain, FFT graphs using the original data and FFT graphs using the newly obtained data after performing some calculations through the results that have been obtained with analysis on the graphs.

FIGURE 2. Bursa Malaysia time domain graph

Looking at the time domain graph for Bursa Malaysia Bhd share price, we cannot determine the stock price pattern because the share price remained the same in early 2015 until mid-2016. However, we can see that the share price for 2016 reached its highest value in August. For 2017 and 2018, we can see the stock price reached its highest value in mid-May. We can also see the second highest share price in June for those two years

In 2019, the highest share price is in mid-January and the second highest share price is in July. This may be because the stock price at the end of 2018 is higher than most stock prices in 2019 and the stock price starts to decline starting in early 2019. However, we can see that the two stock price values do not have much difference.

The hypothesis that can be made from the analysis of the time domain graph for the share price of Bursa Malaysia Bhd is that the share price will start to increase in May until August. This may be due to the fact that there are festive days such as Hari Raya Aidilfitri or Hari Raya Aidiladha between the months.

FIGURE 3. Bursa Malaysia FFT graph

Using the data obtained from the FFT graph above and equation (2) the following values are obtained:

$$m_1 = 12.213, f_s = 1 \text{ sample/day}, N = 2048, f_m = 5.9634 \times 10^{-3} \text{ and } 168 \text{ days/cycle.}$$

Through the calculations that have been made for Bursa Malaysia Berhad, we find that the cycle for the stock price reaches its highest value (peak value) every 168 days. This means that the stock price reaches its peak value twice a year.

CONCLUSION

Through the results of the analysis of the time domain graphs, we can conclude that stock prices will often rise when significant events occur. For example, when looking at the results from the stock price analysis of Bursa Malaysia Berhad, we find that the stock price reached its highest value during the beginning of the year or mid-year. This may be due to the presence of festive days in those months such as Chinese New Year, Hari Raya Aidilfitri and Aidiladha.

Using Apple Inc. stock price analysis results meanwhile, we find that stock prices reach their highest value from October until the end of the year. When we look back at the history of Apple Inc., we find that the company usually announces and releases many products starting in October each year. So, we can conclude that the stock price of Apple Inc company increases when there is the production of new products by the company.

Through the analysis of the FFT graph we find that almost all the selected stock prices have a cycle of 168 days / cycle. This means that all selected companies achieve the highest share price at least twice a year. When compared to the results of time domain graph analysis, the results of these FFT graphs can be considered accurate. This is because the highest and second highest share prices obtained through time domain graphs do not actually have a significant difference in terms of value.

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